

One of the most important aspects of deciding on a **marketing strategy** is deciding on the way you want to communicate to your potential partners or clients. Here are some of the most important things to consider.

#1 Figure Out Who Is The Person You'd Like To Reach

One of the most important aspects of creating an **effective message** is knowing what kind of person it is intended for. You should think of the **job position, age, and level of expertise** of the people that are most relevant to your business goal. The marketing **message** should be **largely different** depending on whether you are looking to contact a **teacher**, a **school director**, or a potential **business partner**. Try to determine what motivations and challenges are specific to that person and identify their barriers and fears.

#2 Pick A Communication Tone

Basing on the persona defined in the above tip you should decide on your communication tone for the text. Being entirely technical might not work with some people, but always strive to appear professional. Choose whether you should concentrate on **describing the benefits** of your educational platform from the **perspective** of a **student**, a **teacher**, or an **institution**. Different approaches will yield different results depending on the persona you are targeting!

#3 Test Different Approaches

Make sure that you are noting which approaches are effective and **iterate** on them. It's possible that your initial expectations about the ideal target group will be wrong, so don't hesitate to **try new tools** when the old approach didn't bring the expected results. The key to successful marketing communication is testing different approaches!